

NORMAL AND PATHOLOGICAL PHYSIOLOGY

ГЕМОДИНАМИЧЕСКОЙ ПЕРЕСТРОЙКЕ СОСУДОВ РЕПРОДУКТИВНЫХ ОРГАНОВ У ЖЕНЩИН ПРИ НЕКОТОРЫХ ПАТОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПРОЦЕССАХ

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HEMODYNAMIC RESTRUCTURING OF THE VESSELS OF REPRODUCTIVE ORGANS IN WOMEN WITH CERTAIN PATHOLOGICAL PROCESSES

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Аннотация

Сосудистая система и тканевая структура маточной трубы и эндометрия характеризуются высокой пластичностью – способностью перестраивается к разнообразным приспособительным перестройкам стенки сосудов, а тканевые структуры при меняющихся условиях гемодинамики подвергаются гиперплазии с последующей редукцией в соответствии с меняющимися условиями функционирования органов при трубной беременности и гиперпластические процессы эндометрия

Abstract

The vascular system and tissue structure of the fallopian tube and endometrium are characterized by high plasticity - the ability to rebuild itself to various adaptive restructuring processes of the vascular wall, and structure of the tissues under the changing of hemodynamic conditions undergo hyperplasia with subsequent reduction in accordance with the changing conditions of organ which functions during tubal pregnancy and hyperplastic processes of the endometrium.

Ключевые слова: маточная труба, эндометрия, перестройка сосуды, внематочная беременность, гиперпластические процессы.

Keywords: fallopian tube, endometrium, vascular restructuring, ectopic pregnancy, hyperplastic processes.

The aim of the study. The purpose of this study was to study the hemodynamic restructuring of the vessels of the reproductive organs in women during certain pathological processes.

Materials and methods of research. A morphological study was performed on 27 women who underwent surgery for tubal pregnancy (TP) using the laparoscopic method. Prospective uterine examination (diagnostic curettage) of 33 reproductive-age patients with hyperplastic pathological processes without malignancies. Sections were stained using standard histological methods. Statistical analysis was performed using the Statistica 6.0 application package, with averaged data calculated using the "M ± m" calculation.

Research results and their discussion. The main components of the female reproductive organ are the uterus, fallopian tubes, ovaries and their appendages. With age-related and pathological changes playing a

significant role is played by compensatory and structural changes of walls and nutrient vessels of the organ. It should be noted that to date, pathomorphological changes in the structure of the walls of the fallopian tube vessels in patients with TP remain poorly studied [1-2].

In connection with the development of new directions in the accurate diagnosis of diseases of the internal genital organs of women of reproductive age, there is a need for a detailed study of the compensatory mechanisms of the vessels of the fallopian tubes and uterus in TP and hyperplastic processes in women of reproductive age and the development of effective diagnostic methods.

The results of these studies may not only provide an opportunity to understand the inadequacy of the study of the morphogenesis of this disease, but also re-

solve the issue of diagnosis and justification of the rational scope of surgical intervention in patients with this pathology.

The blood supply to the uterus and fallopian tubes is provided primarily by the uterine arteries and, to some extent, by the ovarian artery. These arteries run perpendicular to the organ axis along the lateral margins of the uterus and longitudinally along the oviduct, and are located beneath the serosa. Morphometric analysis shows that tubal pregnancies are characterized by the presence of a dilated fallopian tube. The length of the fallopian tubes varied from 7 to 11 cm, averaging 9.0 ± 0.3 cm. At the same time, an increase in the thickness of the fallopian tube was observed, with a diameter ranging from 2.0 to 4.3 cm. A study of pathological changes in the fallopian tube wall during tubal pregnancies after laparoscopic surgery revealed that the organ undergoes changes in all layers of the fallopian tube. In the wall of the organ, structural morphological changes and vascular reorganizations mainly depend on the location of the invasion of the fertilized egg; this process is often localized in the myosalpinx and rarely in the subserous layer of the oviduct wall, creating the possibility of perforation of the organ wall in the invasion zone or promoting the development of adhesions with adjacent organs [3].

The morphological picture of the ectopic pregnancy revealed the presence of elements of the fertilized egg and trophoblastic tissue in the dilated fallopian tube, hemodynamic shifts, hemorrhage, edema of the connective tissue membrane, and, frequently, chorionic villi growing into the folds of the mucosa and muscular membranes. Histological examination of serial sections of the fallopian tube in the area of fertilized egg implantation revealed a decrease in the number of chorionic villi, characterized by hyalinosis of the endosalpinx, myosalpinx, serous layer (perisalpinx), and mesosalpinx, resembling chronic nonspecific productive salpingitis. It was established that progressive changes occur in the area of fertilized egg implantation during tubal pregnancy. The serous layer of the oviduct, involved in the pathological process, underwent significant pathomorphological and compensatory vascular changes.

Tissue edema was accompanied by breakdown of the mesothelium layer and hemodynamic disturbances within the organ system, characterized by dilation and engorgement of blood vessels, particularly the venous components of the microcirculatory system. Destructive pathological changes in the tissue and cellular structures of the organ's serous layer (mesothelium, limiting membrane, superficial and deep cribriform layers of collagen and elastic fibers) were also detected. These changes led to thickening of the serous membrane due to swelling and edema of the connective tissue layer. Compared to the control group, collagen fibers increased in number. In large areas of the serous membrane of the fallopian tube, the mesothelium was thickened and shed, and the mesothelial cells became swollen, edematous, and deformed. The walls of some microvascular vessels were thickened due to collagen proliferation, clearly indicating the transformation of a chronic, productive, infiltrative inflammatory process.

The most compensatory changes were noted in the capillaries located beneath the mesothelium, including edema, endothelial cell damage, microthrombosis, and changes in arteriole-arteriolar and arteriole-venular anastomoses. The venular-arteriolar index in this oviductal membrane with TP was 1.29 versus 1.14 in the comparison group, and the arteriole-venular index was 0.6 versus 0.75 in the comparison group, a 15.5% decrease.

In our study, we sought not only to present information on the normal characteristics of vascular-tissue relationships in the uterus but also to identify specific criteria for certain hyperplastic pathological processes. Given the highly diverse pathomorphology of the uterus, we decided to trace the patterns of microcirculatory bed transformations in some of the most frequently encountered clinical processes: endometritis, endometrial polyps, and endometrial hyperplasia. Endometritis is a prominent representative of a group of acute inflammatory diseases and, for many years, was mistakenly considered a clinically insignificant pathology in cases of asymptomatic inflammation. Studying hemodynamics in the uterine wall in various forms of hyperplastic processes will contribute to the development and improvement of methods for the differential diagnosis of endometrial hyperplastic processes in reproductive age [4-5].

It is known that hyperplastic processes in the endometrium of the uterus are characterized by hypervascularization of its wall, the cause of which is considered to be venous or arterial plethora [6-7].

The studied material showed that during the inflammatory diseases of the uterus, hyperplastic processes and restructuring of all components of the microcirculatory bed of the organ occur. All intraorgan vessels undergo adaptive and pathological changes. Adaptive transformations of terminal vessels occur in a morphofunctional sequence, characterized by the mobilization of reserves, multiplication of blood flow pathways, and hemodynamics. An increase in the capacity of the microcirculatory bed is observed due to the filling of all exchange vessels and the growth of the capillary network, the appearance of tortuosity, and an increase in vascular parameters. Arterioles with a diameter of 18.4 ± 1.3 μm and precapillaries in places are dilated to 15.1 ± 0.9 μm , and capillaries – 11.3 ± 1.1 μm , postcapillaries – 24.6 ± 1.4 μm , venules and arteriole-venular anastomoses are dilated, the venular-arteriolar index increases from 1.23 to 1.45, and the athero-venular coefficient from 0.53 to 0.65. The network of blood capillaries of the mucous membrane is represented by capillaries of folds and capillaries surrounding the glands. Under the influence of the inflammatory process in the intraorgan system of the mucous membrane, a violation of the permeability of capillaries and vessels occurs. The venous capillary network is highly developed and many times exceeds the arterial bed. The walls of dilated arterioles and venules, compared to control vessels, have fewer rows of smooth muscle cells, which are spaced more widely. Functional disturbances in the microvascular bed trigger the development of pathohistological changes in the uterine mucosa and determine their transformation [6]. Mucosal folds are enlarged, glands are dilated, and very deep

folds can be seen in cross-sections. The number of glands in the mucosa is significantly greater than in the control group, and the glands rarely have the appearance of deep tubular sacs.

Hyperplastic processes are observed in the stroma of the uterine mucosa, with increased lymphohistiocytic infiltration around capillaries, glands, and in the connective tissue of the uterine base. During removal of endometrial polyps, histological examination revealed the presence of glandular and glandular-fibrous polyps, most commonly.

Along with the aforementioned adaptive mechanisms, we have identified destructive changes in individual components of the microcirculatory bed, particularly in the venous section, indicating functional failure of the vascular organ system. This may be due to the disease's duration—more than 5 years.

Conclusion. The vascular system and tissue structure of the fallopian tube and endometrium are characterized by high plasticity - the ability to rebuild itself to various adaptive restructuring processes of the vascular wall, and structure of the tissues under the changing of hemodynamic conditions undergo hyperplasia with subsequent reduction in accordance with the changing conditions of organ which functions during tubal pregnancy and hyperplastic processes of the endometrium. Consequently, the functional significance of microvessels determines their structure, which obviously should be taken into account when conducting various diagnostic and therapeutic procedures.

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